

AI-Driven Prognostic Models for Pediatric Traumatic Brain Injury: Enhancing Outcome Prediction and Diagnosis

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Background

AI and machine learning models are transforming pediatric TBI management by improving diagnostic precision, prognostic assessment, and CT scan decision-making. Given the heightened vulnerability of the developing brain, these technologies help mitigate risks associated with radiation exposure while enhancing outcome predictions, ultimately leading to safer and more effective patient care.

Introduction

- Around 475,000 children experience TBI annually, making it a leading cause of death and long-term disability in children. Common causes include falls, motor vehicle accidents, and sports injuries¹.
- Pediatric TBI diagnosis is more complex than adult TBI due to age-related variations in injury presentation, requiring more precise evaluation tools like CT scan².
- Head CT scans expose children to harmful radiation, increase healthcare costs, and while TBI itself can result in cognitive, motor, and behavioral impairments, unnecessary CT scans can add further long-term risks.
- AI and ML models enhance diagnostic accuracy, predict outcomes, and assess CT scan necessity, reducing unnecessary imaging and improving clinical decisions³.

Aim : This study aims to explore the role of AI and ML models in enhancing diagnostic accuracy and predicting outcomes in pediatric traumatic brain injury (TBI).

Figure 1. Pediatric TBI differs from adults due to ongoing brain development, higher neuroplasticity, increased cerebral blood flow, and a larger, softer skull. These factors heighten injury risk and long-term cognitive, learning, and behavioral impacts. Created in BioRender. Putri, C. (2025) <https://BioRender.com/f12o379>

Methodology

- A search was conducted from January 15 to January 25 2025 in PubMed, Scopus, and the Cochrane Library from January 2015 to January 2025 using the search terms: pediatric brain injury or pediatric TBI, artificial intelligence or machine learning or deep learning), prognosis, clinical outcomes, prediction, MRI, CT.
- This study focuses exclusively on pediatric TBI cases from birth to 18 years, excluding adult TBI, non-TBI brain injuries, and animal models. Studies without AI-based prognosis prediction, neuroimaging data, relevant clinical outcomes, or those limited to case reports, conference abstracts, insufficient data, and non-English publications were not included.

Results

- Among 15 studies, five focused on AI for diagnosis, five on CT scan interpretation, four on prognosis, and one covered both CT use and prognosis.
- Most AI models were artificial neural networks (ANN) or custom-built machine learning (ML) algorithms, highlighting a preference for adaptable, data-driven approaches.
- **Strong Predictive Accuracy:** Most ML models achieve high AUC values (above 90%), indicating strong reliability in diagnosing **pediatric TBI** and predicting **CT scan necessity/prognosis**.
- **Trade-offs Between Sensitivity and Specificity:** Some models, like **Chong et al. and Ellethy et al.**, balance **high sensitivity and specificity**, while others, like **Zou et al.**, prioritize **specificity (100%)** at the cost of lower **sensitivity (34%)**, affecting early detection (**Graph A**).
- **Best Overall Performing Models:** Ellethy et al. and Chong et al. stand out with high AUC, sensitivity, and specificity, making them strong candidates for clinical application for diagnosis.
- **Top Performers for CT Scan Prediction:** Lampros et al. and Tunthanathip et al. stand out with AUC values above 98%, making them highly effective for predicting **CT scan necessity and prognosis (Graph B)**.
- The ML models across studies use different input variables, leading to a lack of standardization and limiting model comparability and generalizability.

Discussion

- Deep learning models (ANN, deep ANN) significantly improve pediatric TBI diagnosis with high accuracy and sensitivity, enhancing early detection and risk stratification^{5,4,6}
- AI models reduce unnecessary CT scans while maintaining diagnostic precision, optimizing resource utilization and minimizing radiation exposure^{6,9}
- False positives remain a concern, requiring further refinement to improve model specificity⁸

- AI models improve pediatric TBI diagnosis with high accuracy, balancing sensitivity and specificity, while reducing unnecessary CT scans and optimizing resources, supporting the development of personalized medicine, though further validation is needed.
- **Small sample sizes** (e.g., **Chong et al.**) limit generalizability—**larger datasets (>10,000 cases)** and **standardization of key variables** are essential for **robust AI adoption**.
- Challenges for AI in TBI include data integration across diverse hospital systems, the need for large-scale validation on high-quality datasets, and ensuring AI assists rather than replaces clinical judgment, with a focus on interpretability and trust

Figure 2. This four-step process breaks down the integration of AI to optimize CT scan use and integrate patient-specific data for the formulation of personalized treatment strategies, while also assessing associated risks in TBI care. Created in BioRender. Putri, C. (2025) <https://BioRender.com/f72u344>

Conclusion

- AI-based pediatric TBI diagnosis, using deep learning models, shows promise for personalized medicine by improving accuracy, early detection, and risk stratification. It reduces unnecessary CT scans, optimizes resources, and maintains diagnostic precision, all while cutting costs.
- Future research should focus on improving model specificity, reducing false positives, and integrating AI into clinical workflows with a focus on interpretability and clinician trust. Large, diverse datasets and the standardization of key variables across institutions are essential for enhancing model generalizability and supporting broader clinical adoption.

References

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